

Additional materials for

Potential of using CO₂ observations over India in regional carbon budget estimation by improving the modelling system

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Figure AM1. Monthly variations in whole-day CO₂ observations and simulations over MHL during 2017. Observed CO₂ variability is shown in comparison with (a) STILT-CS simulations, (b) STILT-EGG4 simulations and (c) global reanalysis products.

Figure AM2. Time series of CO₂ diurnal cycle for different seasons over MHL during 2017 is shown in comparison with (a) STILT simulations. Blue (STILT-CS) and red (STILT-EGG4) curves represent the ensemble average of the STILT simulations using different anthropogenic fluxes. Shaded regions represent the range of the model simulations. (b) Global reanalysis products. Note that STILT provides output only every three hours. Similarly, EGG4 and CarbonTracker provide outputs at a three-hour resolution and CarboScope at a six-hour resolution.

Figure AM3. Seasonal cycle of whole-day CO₂ over MHL during 2017. Time series of monthly mean CO₂ (whole-day) over MHL with (a) STILT simulations. Blue (STILT-CS) and red (STILT-EGG4) curves represent the ensemble average of the STILT simulations using different anthropogenic fluxes. Shaded regions represent the range of the model simulations. (b) Monthly mean CO₂ (whole-day) over MHL in comparison with Global reanalysis products.

Figure AM4. CO₂ time series from MHL during 2017 with (a) STILT simulations. Blue (STILT-CS) and red (STILT-EGG4) curves represent the ensemble average of the STILT simulations using different anthropogenic fluxes. Shaded regions represent the range of the model simulations. (b) Global reanalysis products.

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Figure AM5. An overview of the performances of models (see Sect. 4) during daytime (11:00-16:00 local time) at MHL for different months. Bar plots represent the different RMSE (in teal), systematic RMSE (RMSE_s, in lime green) and unsystematic RMSE (RMSE_u, in orchid) values estimated for each station. MAE (●), observed standard deviation (×) and model standard deviation (+) are overlaid on barplots. The black and blue lines represent the correlation coefficient and index of agreement values, respectively. The left panel show STILT-CS simulations, the middle panel show STILT-EGG4 simulations and the right panel show global products.

Figure AM6. An overview of the performance of models (see Sect. 4) at SDN for different months. Bar plots represent the different RMSE (in teal), systematic RMSE ($RMSE_s$, in lime green) and unsystematic RMSE ($RMSE_u$, in orchid) values estimated for each station. MAE (\bullet), observed standard deviation (\times) and model standard deviation ($+$) are overlaid on barplots. The black and blue lines represent the correlation coefficient and index of agreement values, respectively. The left panel show STILT-CS simulations, the middle panel show STILT-EGG4 simulations and the right panel show global products.

Figure AM7. An overview of the performance of models (see Sect. 4) at NGP for the period March to October. Bar plots represent the different RMSE (in teal), systematic RMSE (RMSE_s, in lime green) and unsystematic RMSE (RMSE_u, in orchid) values estimated for each station. MAE (●), observed standard deviation (×) and model standard deviation (+) are overlaid on barplots. The black and blue lines represent the correlation coefficient and index of agreement values, respectively.

Figure AM8. An overview of the performance of models (see Sect. 4) at NGP for different months. Bar plots represent the different RMSE (in teal), systematic RMSE ($RMSE_s$ in lime green) and unsystematic RMSE ($RMSE_u$, in orchid) values estimated for each station. MAE (\bullet), observed standard deviation (\times) and model standard deviation ($+$) are overlaid on barplots. The black and blue lines represent the correlation coefficient and index of agreement values, respectively. The left panel show STILT-CS simulations, the middle panel show STILT-EGG4 simulations and the right panel show global products.

Figure AM9. CO₂ time series from NTL during 2017 with new STILT simulations with the corrected biospheric component for October-December (see Sect. 6.2). Blue (STILT-CS) and red (STILT-EGG4) curves represent the ensemble average of the STILT simulations using different anthropogenic fluxes. Shaded regions represent the range of the model simulations.

Figure AM10. An overview of the performance of models (see Sect. 4) at NTL with new STILT simulations having corrected biospheric components for October-December (see Sect. 6.2). Bar plots represent the different RMSE (in teal), systematic RMSE (RMSE_s, lime green) and unsystematic RMSE (RMSE_u, in orchid) values estimated for each station. MAE (●), observed standard deviation (×) and model standard deviation (+) are overlaid on barplots. The black and blue lines represent the correlation coefficient and index of agreement values, respectively.

Figure AM11. Variability in STILT CO₂ emission components during daytime (11:00-16:00 local time) over MHL for different seasons. For better comparison with other emission components, 380 ppm is reduced from background components.

Figure AM12. Variability in STILT CO₂ emission components over NTL for different seasons. For better comparison with other emission components, 380 ppm is reduced from background components.

Figure AM13. Variability in STILT CO₂ emission components over SDN for different seasons. For better comparison with other emission components, 380 ppm is reduced from background components.

Figure AM14. Variability in STILT CO₂ emission components over NGP for different seasons. For better comparison with other emission components, 380 ppm is reduced from background components.

Figure AM15. An overview of the performance of models (see Sect. 4) at NTL for the period January to July. Bar plots represent the different RMSE (in teal), systematic RMSE (RMSE_s, in lime green) and unsystematic RMSE (RMSE_u, in orchid) values estimated for each station. MAE (●), observed standard deviation (×) and model standard deviation (+) are overlaid on barplots. The black and blue lines represent the correlation coefficient and index of agreement values, respectively.